

Meeting Report

Observational Medical Outcome Partnership (OMOP) Special Interest Group: Sixth Meeting 06/05/2025

Meeting Actions and Key Notes

- Attendees were invited to send suggestions for future OMOP UK meetings to the HDR UK data standards team via email (data_standards@hdruk.ac.uk).
- Attendees were encouraged to register early for the upcoming [OHDSI UK event](#), as tickets are expected to sell out quickly, and to submit their abstracts for the programme by 9th May

Welcome

The meeting was opened by Geoff Hall (Chief Clinical Data Officer, HDR UK), who welcomed all 119 attendees to the sixth OMOP Special Interest Group meeting and introduced himself.

He then introduced his co-chair, Professor Daniel Prieto-Alhambra (OHDSI UK Node Lead and HDR UK Associate Director). Professor Prieto-Alhambra echoed the welcome and gave a brief overview of the topics to be covered, including updates on OHDSI UK 2025, the HERON-UK network, and OMOP developments in maternity and social care data. The meeting would also feature contributions from the OHDSI vocabulary team, SciForce colleagues, and conclude with time for open discussion.

Presentations

OHDSI UK 2025 Update -(Alex Knight Data Standards Project Manager, HDR UK)

[\[Link to slides\]](#)

- An update was provided on the forthcoming OHDSI UK 2025 meeting, which will take place on Friday 26th September at the Wellcome Trust building. This national event is co-organised by OHDSI UK and HDR UK and aims to bring together all aspects of the OMOP ecosystem—ranging from data mapping and analytics to clinical research and practical applications.
- The programme will include invited presentations, posters, software demonstrations, and lightning talks selected from submitted abstracts. For the first time, the event will also feature exhibitors and sponsors.
- The programme will be structured around two key strands: clinical applications and open-source software. These will run sequentially, rather than in parallel, to allow attendees to benefit from the full agenda.
- Attendees were encouraged to submit an abstract and join the review panel, with both deadlines closing on Friday 9th May. Registration is now open and expected to fill up quickly; those unable to attend are asked to cancel their place. Further details on sponsorship and exhibition opportunities are available online.

Health Data Research UK OMOP Network (HERON UK): Update and plans for Year 2- (Edward Burn University of Oxford)

[\[Link to slides\]](#)

A network comprising seven data partners has been successfully established, encompassing over 57 million patient records drawn from both primary care and hospital settings. This extensive network lays the groundwork for collaborative research using the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) across the UK.

Two pilot studies have been undertaken as part of this initiative. The first focused on the use of antibiotics listed on the WHO 'watch list', with particular attention paid to usage patterns and the demographic characteristics of patients. This study aimed to identify the scope of antimicrobial use and support efforts in antimicrobial resistance monitoring.

The second study examined high-cost medicines (as defined by the NHS). This involved mapping the use of these medicines across selected data partners, identifying trends in their use, and assessing the depth of data coverage across the network.

Lessons learned

- A consistent approach to mapping UK-specific vocabularies—such as Read codes, DM+D, and OPCS-4—is essential for data harmonisation.
- Variation in observation periods across hospital data partners highlighted the need for alignment. Work is underway to create a standardised method and an R package to define study-specific observation periods.
- Standardising key data elements like ethnicity and socioeconomic status (e.g., IMD quintiles) is a priority to ensure comparability across datasets.
- Ethical approval processes differ between sites, underscoring the importance of central coordination and consistent disclosure rules to facilitate multi-site research.

Next steps

- Findings from the pilot studies will be published, and abstracts will be submitted to the OHDSI Europe, OHDSI UK and HDR UK conferences.
- New tools will be developed to support data characterisation and output checking, including the use of ACRO.
- The network will be expanded, with a focus on involving more TREs and NHS SDE environments.
- Plans are in place to initiate externally funded, regulatory-grade studies and to engage in international OHDSI network research.

Maternity and Social Care Data in OMOP- Sinead Brophy (Professor of Data Science in Public Health HDRUK Wales)

[\[Link to slides\]](#)

- The MIREDA project (Mother and Infant Research Electronic Data Analysis) aims to harmonise multiple UK birth cohorts—including those from Bradford, South London,

Scotland, Wales, and CPRD in England—into a single OMOP-standardised core dataset. This will support the creation of a UK-wide federated birth cohort, representing approximately 100,000 new births annually, and allow analysis of both national trends and local policy variations.

- MIREDA links pregnancy and birth data with broader datasets including census records, education, social care, and health visitor data, enhancing capacity for natural experiment research and enabling comparisons across UK regions. Variation in preterm birth rates (ranging from ~6% to ~9.6%) has been observed, though the extent to which this reflects data inconsistencies versus true regional variation remains to be clarified through harmonisation.
- Three £20,000 research funding awards are available to support pilot work using MIREDA, with potential uses including training development or international collaborations. A hybrid workshop will be held in Cardiff on 11th July, in partnership with the International Society for Developmental Origins of Health and Disease.
- Health visitor datasets from England, Scotland, and Wales are being reviewed to assess compatibility with OMOP. Common elements are being mapped using OMOP structure, though some new codes may be required.
- In South London, the eLIXIR cohort is assessed within a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) and undergoing OMOP conversion using tools like White Rabbit, Carrot Mapper, and Athena vocabularies. Mapping rules are developed collaboratively, and synthetic OMOP datasets are generated for shared use in analytics development. Further refinement is needed for representing complex pregnancy data relationships.
- Planned activities for the MIREDA project include evaluating differences between raw and OMOP-transformed maternity data, demonstrating the utility of OMOP for natural experiment research—such as assessing the impact of maternity grants in Scotland—and developing training resources, potentially to be hosted via HDR UK. The team also aims to establish research development groups to support collaborative study design and future grant applications.

OHDSI vocabularies and NHS dm+d- Anna Ostroplets (OHDSI Vocabulary Working Group Team Lead)

[\[Link to slides\]](#)

The presentation provided an overview of OHDSI's vocabulary infrastructure, emphasising its role in achieving both structural and semantic harmonisation across data sources in the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM).

- OHDSI vocabularies support interoperability by linking diverse national terminologies (e.g. NHS dm+d in the UK, NDC in the US) to common reference standards such as RxNorm, enabling multi-country network research.
- The process involves importing source vocabularies, applying in-house harmonisation (crosswalks and hierarchies), and standardising data formats using shared staging tables to ensure consistency and quality assurance.
- The NHS dm+d vocabulary, used to encode UK drug data, was highlighted as an example, with its XML-based structure processed via custom scripts and integrated into the OMOP framework.

- A separate, systematic approach is used for drug vocabularies due to their structured nature, involving attribute-level mapping and the use of RxNorm Extension to accommodate international drugs.
- Community contributions are encouraged via GitHub templates that align with the internal structure, enabling researchers to propose new or updated vocabularies (e.g. for surveys or local drug codes).
- Emphasis was placed on quality assurance as a critical and iterative step throughout the process.
- NHS dm+d vocabulary mapping is currently undergoing a refresh, and community members interested in contributing or learning more are encouraged to consult the GitHub documentation or attend the Vocabulary Working Group meetings.

OHDSI vocabularies and NHS dm+d- Denys Kaduk (Technical Lead- SciForce)

[\[Link to slides\]](#)

The presentation introduced an approach to integrating NHS dm+d into OHDSI standardised vocabularies, highlighting the need for streamlined terminology mapping in the face of fragmented clinical coding systems.

- The team shared their experience as a multi-disciplinary group working on terminology harmonisation, data integration, ETL pipeline construction, and AI-driven healthcare solutions, contributing to over 100 projects globally.
- A key shift described was the move from a centralised to a decentralised model of vocabulary development, enabling clinicians and engineers to submit mapping contributions directly via GitHub, which are reviewed, discussed, and merged through an open workflow.
- The team maintains a mirrored production environment and uses structured collaboration with the OHDSI vocabulary group, ensuring updates are clinically and technically sound.
- Technical challenges faced during dm+d mapping were discussed, including complex legacy SQL scripts, long execution times, missing references, and the need to rewrite outdated functions to meet current vocabulary standards.
- A new tool, *Jackalope*, was introduced—an ML-powered platform designed to automate and optimise medical data mapping, support vocabulary curation, and enhance ETL pipelines while maintaining clinical accuracy through manual validation when needed.
- The presentation concluded by framing the dm+d integration as a significant milestone toward better, more interoperable clinical data and invited continued collaboration via community-driven processes.

Discussion

- A brief Q&A followed the presentation, with discussion centred around the timeline for the updated dm+d vocabulary mapping. It was confirmed that the next OHDSI vocabulary release will be at the end of August, with updated dm+d content expected to

be available for download via Athena from 1st September. Attendees were encouraged to consult the meeting chat for links to GitHub repositories and other shared resources.

- A broader discussion was held on improving knowledge sharing and avoiding duplication of efforts across the OHDSI UK and global community. It was noted that OHDSI UK may serve as an effective intermediary for identifying and escalating nationally relevant issues (e.g. dm+d) to the global OHDSI community.
- Community members were encouraged to engage in active studies and cohort development to enhance their learning and integration within OHDSI processes.
- It was emphasised that local vocabularies like dm+d are treated equally to international ones in the vocabulary ecosystem and welcomed input from the UK community to support mapping and integration efforts. It was suggested that UK members could help by providing early intelligence on upcoming updates to national terminologies like dm+d.
- A cancer-themed meeting was proposed for the next OMOP SIG and more input is sought.

UK Health Data
Research Alliance

Attending Organisations

1. Answer Digital
2. Barts Life Sciences
3. Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Trust
4. DATA-CAN
5. Diabetes Trial Unit - University of Oxford
6. EPAM Systems
7. Genomics England
8. Guys and St Thomas NHS Foundation Trusts
9. Health Data Research UK
10. Health Innovation East
11. Holmusk
12. Imperial College London
13. IQVIA
14. Kings College London University
15. Leeds Teaching Hospital NHS Trust
16. MHRA
17. MRC Biostatistics Unit - University of Cambridge
18. MRC Clinical Trials Unit - University College London
19. National Health Research Institute Taiwan
20. National Perinatal Epidemiology Unit - Oxford University
21. NHS Northwestern London Integrated Care Systems
22. NICE
23. Nuffield Department of Population
24. Nuffield Department of Orthopaedics, Rheumatology and Musculoskeletal Sciences (NDORMS) - University of Oxford
25. OHDSI
26. Optimum Patient Care
27. Our Future Health

28. Promptly Health
29. Public Health Scotland
30. Queen's University Belfast
31. Swansea University
32. The Royal Marsden Hospital
33. Tritonis
34. University College London
35. University College London Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust
36. University Dundee
37. University Hospital Southampton
38. University of Birmingham
39. University of Bristol
40. University of Edinburgh
41. University of Leeds
42. University of Leicester
43. University of Limerick
44. University of Manchester
45. University of Nottingham
46. University of Oxford
47. Wellcome Centre for Human Genetics - University of Oxford